

Grant Agreement No.: 101139070 (SNS JU) DOI number: 10.5281/zenodo.14592217

6G4SOCIETY

D4.2 COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION REPORT

Revision: v.1.0

Work package	WP 4
Task	4.1
Due date	31/12/2025
Submission date	22/12/2025
Deliverable lead	Digital for Planet
Version	1
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Abstract	This report provides a comprehensive overview of the Communication and Dissemination activities related to the 6G4Society project, highlighting its success in exploring how 6G innovation can meaningfully integrate societal, environmental, and economic dimensions from the ground up through targeted outreach, community building, and collaboration with EU initiatives and experts. It focuses on the outcomes and impacts of the communication and dissemination strategy and defines the evaluation measures and tools applied.
Keywords	Communication, Dissemination

www.6g4society.eu

Co-funded by
the European Union

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
Stato Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

Document Revision History

Version	Date	Description of change	List of contributor(s)
V1.0	15/11/2025	50% of content written sent for internal review	Erica Cascone (D4P) Aletta D' Cruz (Martel Innovate)
V1.2	26/11/2025	100% of content written sent for internal review	Erica Cascone (D4P) Aletta D' Cruz (Martel Innovate)
V1.3	16/12/2025	Integration of comments from internal reviewers (PSCE and NOVA)	Erica Cascone (D4P) Christos Tselebis (D4P)
V1.1	17/12/2025	Quality Assurance review	Eva Hajdok (Martel Innovate)
V1.4	19/12/2025	Final formatting	Erica Cascone (D4P) Christos Tselebis (D4P)

DISCLAIMER

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Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

6G4Society project has received funding from the [Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking \(SNS JU\)](#) under the European Union's [Horizon Europe research and innovation programme](#) under Grant Agreement No 101139070. This work has received funding from the [Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation \(SERI\)](#).

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Project co-funded by the European Commission in the Horizon Europe Programme		
Nature of the deliverable:	R	
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page)	✓
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	
Classified R-UE/ EU-R	EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/ 444	
Classified C-UE/ EU-C	EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/ 444	
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* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

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DATA: Data sets, microdata, etc.

DMP: Data management plan

ETHICS: Deliverables related to ethics issues.

SECURITY: Deliverables related to security issues

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents the final results of the 6G4Society communication and dissemination strategy, implemented over the course of the project, running from January 2024 to December 2025. The strategy was designed to ensure effective outreach, increase project visibility, impact and engagement with the objectives of 6G4Society, particularly within the European Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU).

The report opens with an overview of the project vision and the objectives that guided the communication and dissemination efforts. At the heart of the strategy was the goal to communicate 6G4Society's mission, activities, and results to a wide and diverse audience, including researchers, industry professionals, policymakers, civil society, and the general public, while ensuring alignment with values of sustainability, trustworthiness, and ethical innovation.

A wide range of communication activities and tools were deployed to ensure the visibility and accessibility of the project's outputs. These included:

- A strong and coherent brand identity;
- Robust online presence via the project website, social media, digital digests, and press releases;
- Dynamic offline communication activities featuring participation in events, workshops, scientific publications, promotional materials, and the launch and dissemination of a citizens' survey and public information package.

In parallel, the project built strategic synergies with the SNS JU ecosystem and other related initiatives, contributing to shared outreach efforts and amplifying the project's visibility through coordinated actions such as participation in the SNS Communication Task Force, SNS Journal contributions, and webinars.

The 6G4Society Final Event served as a culmination of the project's outreach efforts, gathering key stakeholders to showcase results, reflect on lessons learned, and foster further collaboration.

To evaluate performance, the strategy included a detailed framework for monitoring activities and measuring success against pre-defined Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). The coordinated and adaptive nature of the 6G4Society communication and dissemination strategy ensured that project outcomes were widely shared, stakeholder engagement was maximised, and the groundwork was laid for ongoing conversations around the societal dimensions of 6G development.

As the project concludes, the communication assets, partnerships, and insights developed during its implementation provide a strong foundation for future initiatives. Next steps include the continued dissemination of project outcomes through partner networks, contributions to ongoing SNS JU activities, and the potential reuse and adaptation of the strategy and materials by other projects working towards socially responsible 6G innovation.

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ABBREVIATIONS

5GPPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
6G4Society	6G4Society
6G-IA	6G Smart Networks and Services Industry Association
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
D	Deliverable
DG	Directorate-General
EC	European Commission
ETHICNET	International Workshop on Value-driven Ethical Networking in 6G
ESEE	European Society for Ecological Economics
EU	European Union
GA	General Assembly
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HEI	Higher education institution
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IoT	Internet of Things
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KSI	Key Sustainability Indicator
KVI	Key Value Indicator
M	Month
MWC	Mobile World Congress
PSCE	Public Safety Communications Europe Forum
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprise
SNS JU	European Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

1 INTRODUCTION

As the development of 6G advances, questions of acceptability, trustworthiness, and societal relevance are no longer peripheral, they are central to its legitimacy. It is no longer sufficient for emerging technologies to be technically viable or economically feasible; they must also align with ethical expectations, contribute to sustainability, and reflect shared social values. 6G4Society has worked towards addressing this challenge by exploring how 6G innovation can meaningfully integrate societal, environmental, and economic dimensions from the ground up.

To support this broader vision, 6G4Society implemented a comprehensive communication and dissemination strategy designed to ensure impactful outreach, meaningful engagement, and wide visibility of project outcomes. The strategy was tailored to key stakeholder groups, particularly within the SNS JU ecosystem, and focused on fostering trust, building synergies, and supporting knowledge exchange throughout the project lifecycle.

The strategy was first outlined in D4.1 Dissemination and Communication Strategy and Plan, and this final report details its implementation between **January 2024 and December 2025**.

The communication and dissemination plan aimed to:

- Identify and engage target audiences across industry, academia, policy, and civil society, with a focus on the SNS JU ecosystem.
- Deploy a coherent mix of methods, tools, and promotional materials tailored to diverse stakeholder needs.
- Execute a structured programme of activities and exploit emerging opportunities to enhance visibility and engagement.
- Apply clear procedures for implementation, monitoring, and evaluation to ensure consistent quality and alignment with project goals.

Throughout the project, 6G4Society developed and deployed content, tools, actions, and events that significantly strengthened awareness and engagement. The strategy served as the foundation for all outreach efforts, providing clear guidance to consortium members and supporting coordination across communication channels. These efforts enhanced collaboration, supported partnership development, and helped ensure effective dissemination of results.

This deliverable presents the outcomes of those efforts, highlighting the impact achieved through targeted communication activities, including social media outreach, stakeholder engagement, event participation, and public-facing dissemination. It demonstrates how 6G4Society successfully contributed to building a more inclusive, transparent, and value-driven foundation for future 6G development.

2 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION STRATEGY

This section provides an overview of the communication and dissemination framework implemented by the 6G4Society project, describing how its vision, objectives, tools, and outreach activities were translated into a coherent and value-driven strategy. Communication played a central role in supporting the project's mission to embed societal, environmental, and ethical values into the development of future 6G technologies, while ensuring that project results were visible, accessible, and meaningful to a broad range of stakeholders.

The “project vision” section introduces the conceptual foundations guiding all communication and dissemination activities. 6G4Society addressed the dual challenge of achieving advanced technical performance in 6G while integrating sustainability, ethics, and social acceptance by design. To this end, the project actively engaged stakeholders from across the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) ecosystem, as well as policymakers, regulators, civil society organisations, the media, and European citizens. Communication efforts were designed not only to disseminate results, but also to foster trust, understanding, and informed dialogue on the anticipated societal impacts of 6G.

Building on this vision, section “objectives of the strategy” defines communication as a transversal activity supporting all work packages. **The strategy aimed to raise awareness of the 6G4Society project and its results, promote social acceptance of 6G, and ensure that accurate and unbiased information reached European citizens.** A key objective was to engage a critical mass of relevant stakeholders to support validation, uptake, and reuse of project outputs. **Close collaboration with the SNS JU programme and alignment with related European research and innovation initiatives were prioritised** to maximise synergies and reinforce the project's role within the wider 6G ecosystem.

Recognising the importance of coherence between values and practices, the section “sustainable approach to communication and dissemination” describes how **sustainability principles were embedded in communication activities.** The project prioritised digital formats for meetings and events, minimised the use of physical materials, promoted online distribution of resources, and worked with suppliers applying environmentally responsible practices.

Section “communication and dissemination tools and channels” presents **the practical implementation of the strategy.** Furthermore, the project website is presented as the central dissemination hub, hosting project outputs, news, multimedia content, and engagement tools. The website also enabled **systematic monitoring of communication performance through GDPR-compliant analytics.** Subsections outline improvements made to the homepage to enhance accessibility and visibility of key results and the role of regularly updated news items and a quarterly digital digest in maintaining structured and ongoing communication with stakeholders and subscribers. Audiovisual communication is addressed through the description of the **project's video portfolio**, which included introductory videos, expert interviews, thematic discussion series, recorded webinars, and end-of-project reflections. **These formats supported the communication of complex societal and sustainability topics in an accessible and engaging manner.**

The section on “social media presence” outlines the role of **LinkedIn, X, Mastodon, YouTube, and Instagram in amplifying project messages, driving traffic to the website, and fostering interaction with professional, institutional, and public audiences.** Platform-specific approaches, including Advisory Board insights and the 6G4Society Community Forum, supported dialogue and community building. While some quantitative KPIs were not fully reached, performance was assessed through engagement, reach, and interaction indicators, **demonstrating strong qualitative impact.**

Finally, “outreach activities” provides an overview of external **dissemination actions, including media publications, scientific outputs, promotional materials, and participation in workshops, conferences, and policy-relevant events.** These activities positioned 6G4Society within European and international discussions on 6G, sustainability, and societal impact, and facilitated dialogue with experts, policymakers, and citizens.

Overall, this part demonstrates how 6G4Society implemented a **coherent, adaptive, and value-driven communication and dissemination strategy that effectively supported stakeholder engagement, knowledge sharing, and the promotion of sustainable and socially accepted 6G development.**

PROJECT VISION

The 6G4Society project tackled the challenge of balancing two essential goals in 6G technology development: achieving advanced technical performance while embedding societal and sustainability values within the technology itself. To accomplish this, 6G4Society engaged a broad range of stakeholders, including those within the SNS JU ecosystem, civil society, regulators, policymakers, the media, and the general public, to ensure clear and accurate communication regarding the anticipated impacts of 6G.

Leveraging insights from ethics, legal studies, social sciences, and humanities, the project delivered practical tools such as methods, models, guidelines, policy options, and operational recommendations aimed at fostering sustainable and socially accepted 6G technologies and applications. Key outputs included a Technology Acceptance Model for 6G, a framework of Key Sustainability Indicators, as well as policy and operational briefs.

The main objectives of 6G4Society have been the following:

- Generate a better understanding and shared knowledge of the aspects influencing public acceptance of 6G technologies.
- Support the development of a European Union (EU) consensus framework for a value-based, sustainable, and ethics-driven approach towards 6G and its subsequent promotion through the 6G EU and global standard-setting process.
- Engage and reach out to public audiences to build 6G social acceptance.
- Empower the 6G community to reflect EU policy and legislation into technology solutions for future networks’ development and services.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STRATEGY

Key goals of 6G4Society were to promote acceptance of 6G in the general public, to understand potential obstacles to it, and to spread correct and adapted information about the technology and its development to European citizens. Communication has therefore been a critical part of the project activities and played an essential role in supporting all WPs and their outputs.

The main objectives of the communication and dissemination strategy were the following:

- Ensure broad visibility and raise awareness about 6G4Society, spreading knowledge about the project and its results, establishing a distinctive and recognisable identity that supported marketing efforts.
- Reach, stimulate, and engage a critical mass of relevant stakeholders to ensure that:

- 6G4Society activities were effectively and properly disseminated to the targeted audiences for maximum participation and promotion;
 - Accurate and unbiased information about the development of 6G reached European citizens;
 - The results of the project were effectively showcased, leading to the validation and use of the end products by the relevant stakeholders.
- Ensure close collaboration with the SNS JU programme and projects, while establishing liaisons with relevant initiatives in research and innovation domains.

SUSTAINABLE APPROACH TO COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION

The 6G4Society communication and dissemination approach actively considered the sustainability principles for the organisation of events and the production of communication materials. For this purpose, 6G4Society:

- Organised, whenever possible, virtual meetings and workshops instead of face-to-face events.
- Avoided using material resources where possible (avoiding printing flyers when unnecessary and promoting the online download, producing promotional materials using recycled materials, and avoiding single-use products, for example).
- Worked with suppliers (printers, caterers, etc.) that use sustainable products and materials.

3 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION TOOLS AND CHANNELS

The following section presents 6G4Society's brand identity and how it ensured recognisable and consistent visibility across its activities and communication channels. The final part of the section provides an overview of the main communication actions carried out during the project, including the website, social media channels, digital digest, press releases, events, promotional material and publications.

BRAND IDENTITY

As a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) project co-funded by the European Commission (EC), a clear brand identity for the project has been established to ensure consistent visibility in our communication and dissemination activities. Being a CSA within the SNS JU, the [6G SNS Communication and Brand guidelines](#) lay an essential foundation for 6G4Society's brand identity, colour palette, and typography.

The visual identity and guidelines were established at the initial stage of the project to ensure a strong and unique brand. They have been integrated into all promotional and dissemination materials produced during the project and have been used by all project partners in their communication activities. **The complete description of the 6G4Society brand identity, including visual elements and usage guidelines, is provided in Deliverable D4.1 Dissemination and Communication Strategy and Plan.**

WEBSITE

The [website](#) provided a one-stop hub for the presentation and promotion of the project's activities and to this end, several measures have been implemented, namely:

- Gathered email addresses of interested users thanks to a subscription form available on all pages. This mailing list helped us spread the activities of the project through a periodic e-newsletter and digital digest. This mailing list supported the spreading of the citizens' survey as it was launched, and a reminder to fill it out was also sent to the mailing list.
- Encouraged partners to submit their news related to 6G4Society to the project website for republishing to the broader audience. This strengthened the website's relevance, as well as increased its reach and impact.
- Encouraged partners to repost news of direct and indirect interest from partners and the general media. This showed that 6G4Society was involved and engaged in the larger world.
- Organised and aggregated news articles by topic and relevance to improve the ability to share, e.g., via social channels, especially when dealing with calls to action such as participation in events. This allowed the project to maximise the value of its communication outreach.

The project website served as a comprehensive platform to assess the effectiveness of 6G4Society's communication and dissemination efforts. This was achieved by carefully analysing web analytics data. The 6G4Society consortium utilises [Matomo](#) as its web analytics software platform to obtain detailed reports on the project's communication campaigns, website visits, acquisitions, and overall website performance. Importantly, Matomo aligns with

European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) standards and safeguards the ownership of collected data.

The following figure shows the analytics of the website visits since launching the website. It shows that there has been a total of 16,354 visits to the website, with 38,754 page views. A more detailed breakdown can also be found in the following Figure.

FIGURE 1: 6G4SOCIETY'S WEBSITE ANALYTICS

Homepage

The 6G4Society website homepage was revised during the project **to improve clarity, accessibility, and overall user experience**. In particular, ahead of the mid-term checkpoint in June 2025, the homepage content and structure were reviewed and updated to make **key project achievements, resources, and outputs more easily accessible to visitors**. These updates aimed **to better highlight the project's main results**, including deliverables, reports, publications, and multimedia content, while ensuring a more reader-friendly presentation for a broad audience. The revision supported a seamless website experience and reinforced the website's role as a central entry point to the project's knowledge and dissemination activities.

FIGURE 2: 6G4SOCIETY HOMEPAGE

FIGURE 3: NEW 6G4SOCIETY HOMEPAGE

News items and digital digest

The website's news section has been regularly updated with project developments and relevant events, using targeted keywords to inform the audience and increase traffic and engagement.

FIGURE 4: DIGITAL DIGEST ON LINKEDIN

These news items, along with announcements and event highlights, were consolidated into a digital digest published approximately every three months on the website, which was also promoted on the 6G4Society social media channels for wider reach. A snapshot of each issue was also shared via email with contacts subscribed through the mailing list.

6G4SOCIETY January 2025

THE PROJECT CITIZEN SURVEY THE EVENTS

Digital Digest January 2025

January 30, 2025 Digital Digest

6G and Sustainability: Shaping the Next Generation of Connectivity

As the world moves toward the design and development of 6G, sustainability is becoming an essential pillar within the telecom industry. This article talks about the future of telecommunications, addressing key aspects of environmental sustainability and how these issues relate to societal and economic dimensions of sustainability.

It also introduces our latest [Deliverable 1.1](#), where you can learn more about societal aspects in 6G technology: concerns, acceptance models and sustainability indicators.

[Read more](#)

6G4Society Deliverable
D1.1 Societal aspects in 6G Technology: Concerns, acceptance models and sustainability indicators

Workshop on Key Value Indicators: book your calendars!

On 6 February 2025, join us for our "Objective and Subjective Approaches to Key Value Indicators" Workshop - an event designed to blend expert insights with active collaboration to shape how social and sustainability values are measured in SNS JU projects.

[Sign up here](#)

6G4SOCIETY TRIALSNET
TrialsNet is powered by Grant Holistic Research

FIGURE 5: DIGITAL DIGEST EXAMPLE

The digest featured updates on project activities, deliverables and outputs. Each edition included key highlights, links to major outcomes, upcoming events, and a dedicated space for partner interviews, allowing readers to learn more about the organisations behind the project and their perspectives on 6G4Society. It also served as a one-stop resource for all upcoming events focused on 6G and sustainability, including events organised by 6G4Society and other projects within the SNS JU community. The digital digest also played a key role in promoting the citizens' survey, the 6G information packages, and the 6G4Society Community Forum. Additional mailings (e.g., event invitations, consultations) were sent when information could not wait for the next digest release.

A subscription function on the website allowed visitors to register, ensuring GDPR compliance for all communications.

The first digest was published in April 2024 (M04). In total, 8 digital digests were published, receiving around 541 views. The 6G4Society mailing list had 71 total subscribers.

Each edition of the Digital Digest was also actively promoted through the 6G4Society social media channels, in particular LinkedIn, to further extend its reach beyond website visitors and mailing list subscribers.

These posts contributed to increasing visibility and engagement with project outputs among the professional and research community. As an example, one Digital Digest post on LinkedIn achieved 97 impressions and reached 50 members organically, generating 10 engagements (including 5 clicks and 5 reactions), corresponding to an engagement rate of 10.3% and a click-through rate of 5.2%. This demonstrates the effectiveness of social media promotion in complementing website-based dissemination and email communication activities.

Deviations

Although the KPI for website visits (50,000) has not been fully reached, the project implemented a wide range of actions to maximise visibility, increase traffic, and ensure continuous growth throughout the project duration. Several targeted communication campaigns were carried out, supported by regular news updates, social media promotion, newsletter distribution, and the systematic integration of website links across all dissemination activities and partner channels.

While the number of unique visitors indicates that the initial KPI may not have been fully aligned with realistic outreach potential, an issue that was continuously communicated to the funding authorities, the engagement of website users demonstrates the relevance and usefulness of the content provided. Project resources (including deliverables, brochures, and other dissemination materials) were downloaded a total of 10,875 times. This high number of downloads indicates that visitors who accessed the website actively engaged with and made use of the project's outputs, confirming the effectiveness of the website as a dissemination and exploitation channel despite lower-than-targeted visitor numbers.

Videos

During the lifecycle of the project, 6G4Society produced and released many videos that served as a visual platform for viewers to learn more about the project's vision, goals, activities, and results. All videos were uploaded to the project's [YouTube channel](#), added to the website and disseminated on social media channels.

In addition to the introductory project videos, 6G4Society produced a wide range of interview-based content to highlight key themes and insights emerging from the project. Several videos focused on explaining the core mission of 6G4Society and exploring how sustainability will shape both the development and deployment of future 6G networks.

A dedicated interview series, the **6G4Society Talks**, further expanded on these themes. This format invited experts to discuss questions such as: What is the green digital transition? What role does sustainability play in the development of 6G? Why is public acceptance of new technologies essential? Through these conversations, viewers were able to explore the societal and sociological dimensions of technological innovation, gaining a broader understanding of how 6G will intersect with environmental, economic, and ethical considerations.

FIGURE 6: 6G4SOCIETY VIDEOS ON THE WEBSITE

The video collection also included full recordings of the project's webinars, providing an accessible way for wider audiences to revisit the discussions and presentations delivered throughout the project's lifetime.

To conclude the initiative, a set of end-of-project video interviews with consortium members captured **final reflections on the project's outcomes, lessons learned, and future directions**. Together, these videos formed a comprehensive multimedia portfolio that documented both the technical and societal perspectives driving 6G4Society.

Please find below a comprehensive list of all videos of 6G4Society:

- [What is 6G4Society?](#)
- [What is the green digital transition? How can it, along with 6G, support sustainability?](#)

- [What does the future of 6G hold? How does sustainability play into it? What is the SNS JU's role?](#)
- [Sustainability by design in the development of 6G, how does that look like?](#)
- [How can Key Value Indicators \(KVI\) help us address sustainability concerns?](#)
- [What is the difference between acceptance and acceptability?](#)
- [What is 6G? - 6G4Society](#)
- [6G4Society - Introductory video](#)
- [Why is public engagement important when working on 6G?](#)
- [Shaping the Future of Public Safety: Bridging 5G Innovation and Societal Values](#) (session in collaboration with 6G-PATH, TrialsNet, and FIDAL project)
- [6G for a Sustainable and inclusive future](#)
- [6G4Society: A Human-Centric Vision for the Future](#)
- [Final Interview with Katrina Petersen, PSCE - Understanding KVIs & stakeholder values in 6G | Insights from 6G4Society](#)
- [Final Interview with Flavia Maragno, D4P - What citizens expect from 6G | Insights from 6G4Society](#)
- [Final interview with Dr Monique Calisti, 6G4Society coordinator](#)
- [Final interview with Eleni Chamou, Nova](#)
- [Final interview with Margot Bezzi, CSL](#)

SOCIAL MEDIA PRESENCE

6G4Society established several social media channels to regularly promote project activities and results, while also fostering broader discussions on **themes such as sustainability in technology and Key Value Indicators (KVIs)**. In addition to general awareness-raising, social media was used **strategically to promote project events and to disseminate key deliverables through short, targeted content formats, including visual summaries and concise highlights of main findings, messages, and calls to action**. The project built an active presence on LinkedIn, X (formerly Twitter), Instagram, and Mastodon. All channels are connected to the project website. Below is a brief overview of the 6G4Society approach to each platform.

LinkedIn (1765 Followers)

6G4Society set up its [LinkedIn account](#) at the inception of the project. The LinkedIn profile of 6G4Society helped drive traffic to 6G4Society.eu, and provided a way to promote the project. We mentioned partners' LinkedIn pages when appropriate to create a positive exchange about visibility. We engaged the other initiatives and projects in the SNS JU ecosystem while promoting 6G4Society's activities in the relevant LinkedIn groups with a direct link to the project's page, to further increase the social media audience and diversify the user base of the page by targeting more vertical representatives/managers.

Appropriate hashtags and accounts were identified to maximise the reach and coverage of the 6G4Society LinkedIn channel for the project's content to be found by the target audience, to increase the number of views, likes, and shares, and to increase the number of visitors to the website.

Showcasing Advisory Board insights

As part of our efforts to highlight the collective vision and support of our External Advisory Board, we invited members to share short statements reflecting their views on the project's themes, direction, and societal relevance.

FIGURE 7: ADVISORY BOARD QUOTES ON LINKEDIN

These quotes were provided during and after the Advisory Board’s kick-off meeting, capturing their spontaneous perspectives and reinforcing the importance of their guidance in shaping the project’s work. The quotes were featured prominently across the project’s website, where a dedicated section was created, and shared through our social media channels. This initiative significantly boosted engagement on these platforms, contributing to increased website visits and strengthening the project’s overall online visibility.

6G4Society Community Forum

To extend engagement beyond the consortium and foster dialogue with external stakeholders, [a dedicated LinkedIn community was created for 6G4Society](#). The community forum served as an open space for citizens, policymakers, researchers, industry representatives, and civil society actors to exchange views on the societal, environmental, and ethical dimensions of 6G.

FIGURE 8: 6G4SOCIETY COMMUNITY FORUM

The community provided a platform to:

- Share news, insights, and project updates
- Discuss how next-generation connectivity can support societal needs and sustainability
- Promote inclusive and human-centric digital innovation
- Encourage participation in consultations, surveys, and events
- Build a network of actors interested in shaping responsible 6G policies and technologies

Through this group, 6G4Society aimed to support an ongoing, multi-stakeholder conversation that extends beyond the project's duration and contributes to a broader public debate on the future of 6G in Europe.

X (Formerly Twitter, 88 followers)

6G4Society used X to make meaningful connections with active and relevant audiences (EC and relevant Directorates-General (DGs), policymakers, industry stakeholders, and the general public). It also served as a tool to inform audiences on project workshops, attended events, and other relevant activities of the project.

Appropriate hashtags and accounts were identified to maximise the reach and coverage of the 6G4Society X channel for the project's content to be found by the target audience, to increase the number of views, likes, and shares, and to increase the number of visitors to the website.

Mastodon (20 followers)

Mastodon is a decentralised social media platform that allows users to connect and communicate with others through microblogging in a federated network of independently operated servers. It offers greater control over privacy, fosters community building, and promotes a diverse and inclusive online environment.

Because 6G4Society aims to embed societal and sustainable values into the development of 6G technologies, it is essential for the project itself to proactively support open-source and decentralised internet platforms. Furthermore, the EC has clearly declared its wish to move away from only working with big tech company platforms and following the trend of other tech-related CSAs, such as Next Generation Internet. 6G4Society opened its Mastodon account in February 2024 ([@6G4Society@eupolicy.social](https://eupolicy.social/@6G4Society)) and since then has gained 20 followers.

YouTube (27 followers)

YouTube is an online video-sharing and social media platform. It served as the main channel to communicate 6G4Society's video content, such as interviews with experts or interviews with partners.

6G4Society set up its YouTube account [@6G4Society](https://www.youtube.com/@6G4Society) in February 2024. All videos posted on the YouTube channel have been cross-promoted on the project's other social media channels.

Since February 2024, the project has published 20 videos on YouTube, which have earned 990 total views.

Instagram (35 followers)

Instagram is a visual social media platform used to share concise, engaging content with a broad and diverse audience. Within the 6G4Society communication strategy, Instagram

supported the dissemination of key project updates, visual highlights, and promotional materials related to events, videos, and project activities.

The 6G4Society Instagram account (@6G4Society) was launched in May 2024. Content published on Instagram has been aligned with and cross-promoted through the project's other social media channels to ensure consistent messaging and increased visibility.

Since February 2024, the project has published 15 posts on Instagram, contributing to a growing community and supporting the overall outreach and awareness objectives of the project.

Deviations

While the quantitative KPI related to the total number of social media followers (5,000) was not fully achieved within the project lifetime, the overall performance and effectiveness of the 6G4Society social media activities remain strong when assessed through engagement and reach analytics. Across the active social media channels (LinkedIn, X, Mastodon, YouTube and Instagram), the project generated over 100,000 impressions, over 8.191 post link clicks, an average post engagement rate of 10.7%, nearly 3,000 video views, and over 3,700 post reactions. These indicators demonstrate a high level of interest and interaction with the project's content, well above typical engagement benchmarks for newly established research project accounts. The consortium focused on maximising content quality and relevance rather than follower acquisition alone. This included prioritising posts with high informational value and aligning social media activity closely with key project outputs (deliverables) and participatory actions such as the Citizen Survey. This unmet KPI was transparently and consistently communicated to the funding authorities throughout the project, together with contextual explanations and mitigation measures.

OUTREACH ACTIVITIES

Media publications

Key project updates, announcements, and news items were published through external channels such as professional and thematic platforms, blogs, collaboration portals, and partners' websites. These media publications supported broader visibility and helped position 6G4Society within ongoing discussions on 6G development, sustainability, and digital innovation.

Media publications included:

Press releases:

- [6G4Society Project Sets the Stage for Human-Centric Next-Generation Networks](#)
- [European project reveals how technology can serve people, communities and the planet](#)
- [EU Project 6G4Society Concludes: Shaping a People-Centred and Sustainable Vision for 6G](#)

Media outreach activities:

- [ICTED Information Communication – Technologies Education Magazine](#)
- [6G4Society: From 6G connectivity to sustainable innovation](#)
- [Putting people first: Europe's 6G push for connectivity that serves society](#)

Scientific publications

The consortium maintained an active publication pipeline, contributed to journals, conferences, and expert platforms, and used each submission cycle to refine content and align with relevant calls. The experience also helped identify publication barriers and timing constraints that will inform future dissemination in follow-up initiatives.

FIGURE 9: SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

Below is the list of all scientific publications by 6G4Society:

- [Calisti, M., Aseeva, A., & Onwude, D. \(2025\). 6G Sustainability: Prospective Business Models. Proceedings of the ACM Conference on Information Technology for Social Good \(GoodIT 2025\), Antwerp, Belgium. DOI: 10.1145/3748699.3749820 Available at: https://6g4society.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/118/2025/10/6G4S-paper_ACM-conference-GoodIT25_v2.pdf](https://6g4society.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/118/2025/10/6G4S-paper_ACM-conference-GoodIT25_v2.pdf)
- [Bezzi, M., Volpini, L., & Ratto Vaquer, L. M. \(2025\). 6G4Society: Social Acceptance of 6G Technology. CyberEthics Lab, Rome, Italy.](#)
- [Carwile, L. P., & Bezzi, M. \(2025\). Beyond Adoption: Rethinking Technology Acceptance through a Social Acceptance Framework for 6G. Cyber Social Lab \(CSL\), Rome, Italy.](#)
- [Calisti, M., Petersen, K., Bezzi, M., Carwile, L. P., Maragno, F., & Staheyeff, S. \(2025\). Towards a Sustainable and Socially Accepted 6G for Society.](#)

- [Decorme R, Faye S, Calisti M et al. Towards sustainable 6G: A collaborative call to action for addressing environmental challenges in \(and thanks to\) future mobile networks \[version 2; peer review: 1 approved, 2 approved with reservations\]. Open Res Europe 2025, 4:260 \(https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.18767.2\)](https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.18767.2)
- [Petersen, K., Bezzi, M., Gavras, A., Calisti, M., & Mohnani, P. \(2025\). Value-Driven 6G: The Role of Key Value Indicators in Design and Societal Impact.](#)

Topic	Article URL	Scientific Journal	Conference Papers	Whitepaper /Article
Towards a Sustainable and Socially Accepted 6G for Society – Extended Paper	https://6g4society.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/118/2024/10/6G4Society_ExtendedPaper_final_v4.pdf	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE
Towards sustainable 6G: A collaborative call to action for addressing environmental challenges in (and thanks to) future mobile networks	https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/articles/4-260	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
ICTED Information Communication – Technologies Education Magazine	https://6g4society.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/118/2025/06/ICTEDMAGAZINE-maggio-2025.pdf	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE
Value Approach of 6G The Role of Key Value Indicators in Design and Societal Impact	https://6g4society.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/118/2025/06/Value-Approach-of-6G-The-Role-of-Key-Value-Indicators-in-Design-and-Societal-Impact.pdf	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE
ACM GoodIT Conference proceedings	https://6g4society.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/118/2025/10/6G4S-paper_ACM-conference-GoodIT25_v2.pdf	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE
6G4Society: Social Acceptance of 6G Technology	https://6g4society.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/118/2025/09/Social-Acceptance-of-6G.pdf	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE
Beyond Adoption: Rethinking Technology Acceptance through a Social Acceptance Framework for 6G	https://6g4society.eu/wp-content/uploads/sites/118/2025/09/Beyond-Adoption-Rethinking-Technology.pdf	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE

TABLE 1: SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS TABLE

Deviations

As a Coordination and Support Action (CSA), our project was primarily dedicated to communication, coordination, and stakeholder engagement rather than academic research. While scientific publications provided added value, the original KPI for journal publications (4 scientific publications to journals) did not fully align with the project's core mission. Nevertheless, the project team maximised every available opportunity for meaningful dissemination, actively engaging with stakeholders, showcasing our work across multiple platforms, and ensuring that the project's outcomes reached a wide and relevant audience. Consolidating our collaboration with other SNS-JU projects, we contributed to various white papers as well. In doing so, the team significantly strengthened the project's overall impact.

Promotional materials

A variety of promotional materials were developed to raise awareness of the 6G4Society project and engage stakeholders and citizens. These included flyers, roll-ups, posters, stickers, and eco-friendly tote bags, all featuring consistent branding with the project logo, EU acknowledgment, and relevant web and social media links. Flyers and posters provided clear information about the project’s objectives and activities, while roll-ups and posters were designed to be adaptable for partner events. Branded stickers with QR codes promoted the citizen survey, facilitating easy participation, and tote bags offered a practical, visible means of reinforcing the project’s presence in public settings. Together, these materials supported outreach efforts across both physical and digital channels.

FIGURE 10: PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS

Flyers

Project flyers were created and used to inform interested people about the project’s objectives and activities. Flyers have been uploaded to the 6G4Society website and shared as printed versions during relevant events.

FIGURE 11: 6G4SOCIETY FLYER

Roll-ups and posters

Roll-ups were created, matching the look and feel of the website and the overall project design concept to meet the needs of the project.

Both the roll-ups and the posters have been prepared to raise awareness of the stakeholders and a variety of relevant audiences about the project with succinct textual and graphical information. Printable versions of the posters have also been created and provided to partners to be printed and used at the events they participate in. The design was easily adjustable to the requirements of individual partners, in case an additional or a more specific version is required. The project logo, the EU flag & acknowledgment, along with the 6G4Society website and the social media links, have been displayed on all promotional materials.

6G4SOCIETY

Towards a sustainable and accepted 6G for society

Visit 6g4society.eu

Ensuring that **societal and sustainable values** are properly embedded into **6G**, bringing a **sociological perspective** to **technological development**.

Our goals

- Understand **aspects influencing public acceptance** of 6G;
- Support the development of an **EU consensus framework** for a sustainable 6G;
- Foster **social acceptance of 6G** through public engagement;
- Empower the 6G community to **reflect EU policy and legislation into technology solutions**.

The Consortium

MARTEL INSTITUTE, CoeRthouat, NOVA, FSC Europe, BOS, DIGITAL FOR PLANET

@6g4society, @6g4society@eupolicy.social, @6g4society, info@6g4society.eu

Co-funded by the European Union, 6G SNS

FIGURE 12: 6G4SOCIETY ROLL-UP

Stickers

To support the promotion of the 6G4Society citizen survey, we developed branded stickers featuring a prominently placed QR code to facilitate fast and effortless access. These stickers were distributed at events, conferences, and partner touchpoints, providing a simple but effective way to encourage participation. Their portable and visible design allowed us to extend survey awareness beyond digital channels and into everyday environments where citizens could conveniently scan and respond.

Tote bags

FIGURE 13: 6G4SOCIETY BAG

The project also produced eco-friendly tote bags as a physical promotional asset to increase visibility for the citizen survey and the 6G4Society initiative. The bags featured the project branding, ensuring continued exposure as participants used them in public settings. This approach helped build familiarity with the initiative in a subtle yet consistent way while offering supporters a functional item that reinforced the project's identity and purpose.

EVENTS, WORKSHOPS, AND CONFERENCES

Participation in events, workshops, and conferences has been a key element of 6G4Society's outreach and stakeholder engagement strategy. These occasions served both to present the project's vision and results, and to foster collaboration with other initiatives working on 6G, sustainability, and societal impact.

By the time of this deliverable, 6G4Society has contributed to or co-organised the following events:

Workshops, webinars, and sessions organised or co-organised by 6G4Society

- [Embracing Key Values and Key Value Indicators: How can SNS projects drive sustainable change? \(with FIDAL\) - Online, November 2024](#)

What does it take to ensure that 6G technology maximizes societal, environmental, and economic sustainability? How can Key Value Indicators (KVI) help shape a 6G future that delivers positive impacts for individuals, communities, and businesses alike?

On 21 November 2024, the SNS JU 6G4Society project co-hosted with FIDAL a workshop to explore how KVIs are being defined, implemented, and used by ongoing SNS projects to embed sustainability and societal values into 6G development. Experts shared challenges, best practices, and expected outcomes of working with KVIs while engaging in interactive discussions to align on priorities and impacts.

- [Ensuring 6G Social Acceptance \(with Hexa-X-II\) - Online, November 2024](#)

What does it take to ensure that 6G technology is accepted, trusted, and valued by society? How can projects integrate societal and environmental values by design?

On 6 November 2024, Hexa-X-II and 6G4Society, two European Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) projects, co-hosted a webinar where experts from both projects shared insights on building societal acceptance for 6G. Join our speakers as they discuss frameworks for social acceptance, survey findings on 5G and 6G, and feedback from public administrations. Learn how SNS JU projects are pioneering a multistakeholder approach to develop a connected society that's sustainable, inclusive, and secure.

- [Objective and subjective measures of KV/KVIs: sharing methodological approaches and evaluation instruments \(with TrialsNet\) - Online, February 2025](#)

How can we effectively measure social and sustainability values in 6G research? What methodologies go beyond traditional KPIs to capture these critical dimensions?

On 6 February 2025, 6G4Society and TrialsNet co-hosted a workshop bringing together SNS JU projects and external experts to explore objective and subjective approaches to Key Value Indicators (KVIs). Join our speakers as they discuss cutting-edge methodologies, real-world examples, and collaborative strategies to assess non-technical value outcomes. Learn how projects can integrate KVIs into their work and contribute to a more inclusive, sustainable, and impactful 6G ecosystem.

- [Understanding and Addressing 6G Controversies: Learning from the Past, Building for the Future – 6G4Society Webinar - Online, March 2025](#)

Understanding controversies is a critical step in promoting social acceptance. Controversies are not simply obstacles; they are part of society's negotiation process over technological change. They reflect broader discussions about governance, power, values, and risk distribution. Engaging with these disputes allows us to anticipate concerns, address misinformation, and develop frameworks for a more responsible and widely accepted 6G deployment.

On 26 March 2025, 6G4Society hosted a webinar that explored lessons from past 5G controversies, the evolution of 6G disputes, the role of values and governance, public engagement for trust, and controversy analysis for an ethical EU 6G framework.

- [Special Session at EuCNC 2024: Towards a sustainable and socially accepted 6G for society - Antwerp, June 2024](#)

FIGURE 14: 6G4SOCIETY TEAM AT THE EUCNC 2024

EuCNC & 6G Summit is among the most eagerly awaited telecommunications events of the year. It gathers cutting-edge research and world-known industries and business presenting and discussing the latest research in 5G deployment, 6G exploration and future communications systems. 6G4Society could not miss the event and went to Antwerp (Belgium) from the 3th to the 6th of June to take part in the 2024's edition under the motto "From Vision to Reality". Our Project Coordinator, Monique Calisti (Martel Innovate) and several project partners from CyberEthics Lab., Public Safety Communication Europe, and Digital for Planet participated in a number of sessions to present the project development and lead the conversation on how to embed societal and environmental values into the development of 6G technology. Read more [here](#).

- [6G4Society and 6G Next Generation Networks: What does it take to create a successful ecosystem? - Online, September 2025](#)

This insightful webinar, hosted by the 6G4Society project under the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU), brought together leading experts from Finland and the Netherlands to explore how Europe is shaping the future of sustainable 6G. As the continent prepares for 6G deployment by 2030, the session examined the critical intersection of 6G, AI, and IoT, highlighting the technological, societal, and regulatory foundations needed to build a resilient and sovereign digital ecosystem. The discussion offered strategic insights, real-world examples, and collaborative perspectives for industry, policymakers, researchers, and innovators across Europe and beyond.

- [6G4Society Webinar: A conversation with the Dutch FNS 6G Ethics Board - Online, September 2025](#)

This engaging webinar explored how ethics, inclusion, and human-centered design can and must shape the development of next-generation networks. Hosted by the 6G4Society project, the session featured members of the Dutch FNS 6G Ethics Board and delved into the importance of embedding ethical frameworks into 6G technologies from the outset. As Europe advances toward 6G deployment by 2030, the conversation highlighted the need for a cross-disciplinary approach that goes beyond technical KPIs, introducing Key Value Indicators (KVIs)

as tools for purpose-driven innovation. The session brought together experts from academia, policy, and civil society to reflect on how we can build digital infrastructure that serves sustainability, societal values, and true digital inclusion.

Participation in major conferences and events

- [EuCNC 2024 – 6G Series Workshop by Hexa-X-II - Antwerp, June 2024](#)

6G4Society organised the “Towards a Sustainable and Socially Accepted 6G for Society” session, in collaboration with the FIDAL and BroadEU.net projects. The invited experts explored the integration of privacy, safety, inclusivity, and sustainability into 6G by design, and discussed how Key Values Indicators can be used to measure the success of these integrations, fostering a holistic approach to 6G development. The Citizen Survey was also presented, a unique opportunity for European citizens to share their experiences and opinions about current 5G technology and the upcoming transition to 6G.

- [One6G Summit 2024 – Global 6G Development – Part II - Valencia, September 2024](#)

The one6G Summit 2024, held in the sunny city of Valencia, Spain, proved to be a significant event in the discourse on the future of connectivity. The summit continued its tradition of leading conversations on 6G technology and its potential societal impact. 6G4Society Project Coordinator, Monique Calisti, presented during Session 2: “Global 6G Development – Part II” and addressed the crucial question: How can we harness 6G for society and the environment?

- [Sustainable Places 2024 – Towards Sustainable 6G Mobile Networks - Luxembourg, September 2024](#)

On Wednesday, 25th September 2024, from 14:00 – 15:30, Project Coordinator Monique Calisti contributed to the workshop “Towards Sustainable 6G: A Workshop on Integrating Environmental Considerations in Next-Generation”.

- [EuCNC 2025 – Workshop on Technology Enablers for Sustainable 6G Design - Poznan, June 2025](#)

EuCNC & 6G Summit is among the most eagerly awaited telecommunications events of the year. It gathers cutting-edge research and world-known industries and business presenting and discussing the latest research in 5G deployment, 6G exploration and future communications systems. 6G4Society could not miss the event and went to Poznań (Poland) from the 3th to the 6th of June to take part in the 2025’s edition under the motto “Towards the 6G World”. Project Coordinator, Monique Calisti (Martel Innovate) and several project partners from Cyber Social Lab., Public Safety Communication Europe, and Digital for Planet participated in a number of sessions to present the project development and lead the conversation on how to embed societal and environmental values into the development of 6G technology.

FIGURE 15: PRESENTATION AT THE EUCNC SUMMIT

- EuCNC 2025 – Special Session 7: Social Acceptance as a Catalyst for Sustainable 6G - Poznan, June 2025

Organised and chaired by 6G4Society, this session explored how social acceptance can be meaningfully addressed within the development of 6G technologies. Presentations from several SNS JU projects, including 6G4Society, Hexa-X-II, TrialsNet, SUSTAIN-6G, and FIDAL, focused on approaches to understanding public attitudes, integrating public engagement activities, and building trust and transparency into technology development.

- EuCNC 2025 – Special Session 17: Societal Sustainability Driven by Values – Transforming 6G Through Key Value Indicators - Poznan, June 2025

This session examined the use of Key Value Indicators (KVIs) as a framework to guide the value-driven design of 6G technologies. Co-organised by 6G4Society, the session offered insights into how societal impact can be measured, prioritised, and integrated from the early stages of 6G research.

- PSCE Winter Conference - Brussels, December 2025
- ETSI Security Conference - Sophia Antipolis, October 2025

Poster presentations

- ITU-ETSI Symposium 2024 - Geneva, December 2024
- PSCE Spring Conference 2024 - Vienna, June 2024

Keynote & paper presentation

[ACM GoodIT 2025 - Antwerp, September 2025](#)

Dr. Monique Calisti, CEO of Martel Innovate and Founder and President at Digital for Planet, delivered a keynote on building sustainable digital futures. Her talk highlighted the Digital Environmental Paradox: while digital technologies are vital in addressing today’s challenges, they also create significant environmental and societal costs. She called for sustainability to be treated as a design requirement rather than an afterthought. As part of her reflections, Monique referenced the work of 6G4Society, using it as an example of how projects can embed environmental and societal considerations into the early stages of 6G design.

FIGURE 16: DR MONIQUE CALISTI AT THE ACM GOODIT 2025 IN ANTWERP, SEPTEMBER 2025

4 6G4SOCIETY FINAL EVENT

The final event of 6G4Society took place on 15 December 2025, online. It brought together, among others, representatives from SNS CO-OP and Sustain-6G within the broader ecosystem of SNS JU projects. This collaboration reflects 6G4Society's intent to embed its sustainability- and value-oriented outputs into the broader SNS community.

A full recording of the event can be found [here](#).

Aims and objectives

The 6G4Society Final Event aimed to showcase the project's achievements in integrating societal, environmental, and economic sustainability into 6G technology development. The objectives included:

- Demonstrating how 6G network development aligns technical trajectories with social sustainability.
- Highlighting interdisciplinary approaches and socially relevant use cases.
- Presenting tools, frameworks, and findings developed by 6G4Society, including the Social Acceptance of Technology (SAT), KVI/KSI Framework, KVI Ontology, and Citizen Questionnaire.
- Proposing actionable recommendations for the SNS JU community to ensure future 6G use cases are sustainable, inclusive, and aligned with societal needs.

Definition and agenda

During the event, 6G4Society organised:

- A keynote and sessions presenting the project's work on social sustainability, social acceptance of technology (SAT), and the development of a value-based framework for 6G, with speakers from within the consortium.
- A dedicated session on how societal impact, sustainability, and key-value indicators (KVIs / KSIs) can guide value-driven network design, including practical implementation of a "KVI ontology."
- A panel discussion bringing together actors from industry, research, and standardisation (including representatives from Sustain-6G and SNS CO-OP) to discuss the interconnections among social, environmental, and economic dimensions of sustainability in 6G. This session addressed challenges, trade-offs, and holistic approaches across these pillars.
- A policy-oriented panel to derive lessons learnt, recommendations, and policy directions for future SNS JU initiatives, providing a platform to embed the outputs of 6G4Society into future 6G strategy, standardisation, and deployment processes

Structure and topics

The event was structured around a series of thematic sessions and panels:

1. Opening & Keynote: Strategic positioning and SNS JU's sustainability leadership.
2. Presentation Session: Insights from 6G4Society on citizen engagement, SAT, KVIs, and ontology application.
3. Panel Discussion 1: Interconnection of the three sustainability dimensions.
4. Panel Discussion 2: Policy takeaways and recommendations.

5. Q&A and Wrap-up: Engaging the audience to clarify concepts and gather feedback.

Topics covered included social acceptance, value-driven innovation, citizen engagement methodologies, KVI/KSI frameworks, the KVI Ontology, and interdisciplinary sustainability approaches.

Target audience

The event targeted:

- Members of the 6G4Society consortium and partner organizations.
- SNS JU project teams and associated 6G-IA initiatives.
- Policymakers, regulators, and European Commission representatives.
- Researchers, industry stakeholders, and experts interested in sustainable 6G development.

Branding and visual identity

FIGURE 17: 6G4SOCIETY FINAL EVENT BRANDING

The event followed the 6G4Society branding guidelines, maintaining a consistent visual identity across online materials, presentations, and communications. Elements included:

- 6G4Society logo and SNS JU partnership visibility on slides and registration pages.
- Cohesive color palette and design aligned with previous project communications.
- Use of professionally designed templates for presentations, fact sheets, and visualizations of frameworks (KVI/KSI, ontology, SAT).

Results and outcomes

The Final Event:

- Presented the project's tools, frameworks, and methodologies to the broader 6G sustainability community.
- Engaged stakeholders through interactive Q&A sessions and panel discussions, fostering dialogue on societal impact and sustainability integration.
- Strengthened the handover plan to Sustain-6G, ensuring continuity and usability of project outputs.
- Generated recommendations for the SNS JU community on embedding social sustainability into 6G projects and policy development.
- Raised awareness of interdisciplinary approaches necessary for socially responsible 6G innovation, reinforcing 6G4Society's role as a reference for socially aligned technological development.

As a result of the collaboration and the final event:

- 6G4Society's core tools and frameworks, including the Social Acceptance of Technology (SAT) model, the KVI/KSI Framework, the KVI Ontology, and the Citizen Questionnaire, were formally presented to the SNS community, offering concrete instruments for measuring and steering value-based 6G design.
- The event reinforced the role of social sustainability and citizen-centric values as central components of future 6G development rather than peripheral add-ons, strengthening the strategic alignment between technical innovation, societal values, and European policy priorities.
- Through the participation of SNS CO-OP, Sustain-6G, and other stakeholders, the event helped bridge the gap between research-focused, value-driven frameworks and more deployment- or industry-oriented projects, promoting a shared vision of sustainable, inclusive 6G.
- Concrete recommendations for short- and long-term actions were produced, intended to support the SNS JU community in embedding sustainability, inclusiveness, and social acceptance into forthcoming 6G use cases and standardisation efforts.

5 SUPPORTING CITIZEN ENGAGEMENTS ACTIVITIES

Reaching more than 1'800 respondents, the 6G4Society citizens' survey has been an essential pillar of the project as it served as the main tool to gather the public's perception of 5G and 6G as well as their wants and fears related to 6G. The survey has been distributed and promoted through the project's social media channels and the digital digest. 6G4Society also engaged other projects within the SNS JU network to promote it within their circles through their social media channels, newsletters, and mailing lists.

Citizens' associations and universities were contacted to promote the survey within their networks. Targeting these actors allowed for a broad range of socio-demographic groups to be reached (young students through universities, e.g.). Furthermore, the possibility of presenting the project and promoting the survey through a project stand, posters, flyers, or a class shout has been explored with the universities contacted.

A specific flyer as well as a sticker with a QR code leading straight to the survey has been designed and distributed at relevant events, workshops, and conferences. A QR code has been integrated at the end of the 6G4Society general presentation so that any time a partner presented the project, they led the participants to the survey.

D2.3 Report on Public positions on 6G technology, with the final analysis as well as guidelines for Industry and Policy Makers, explains more in-depth how the survey has been designed and promoted.

Information package and its promotion

6G4Society created an explanatory information package for non-experts in different languages. This package aimed to foster a better understanding of the potential societal, environmental, and public health effects of 6G and related technologies, and to make the public audience aware of the benefits, opportunities, and risks related to 6G technology-wide deployment. The information package included info sheets, videos, and infographics.

Below is an overview of the material:

- 5 Infosheets, translated into 5 languages
- History Through Wireless Generations: Tracing the evolution of mobile networks from 1G to 6G.
- What's in it for me? How 6G Affects You and the Environment: Exploring the societal and environmental impacts of 6G.
- Transforming Learning with 6G: Highlighting how 6G can revolutionise education and digital accessibility.
- 6G and Smart cities: Building the future: Exploring how 6G enables connectivity and contributes to building smart cities.
- 6G for Accessibility: Inclusion through Technology
- Infographics - To share the content of the Infosheets across different channels
- "What is 6G?" Animated Video

The information package has been distributed and promoted through the project's social media channels and the digital digest. 6G4Society also engaged the other projects within the SNS JU network to promote it within their circles through their social media channels, newsletters, and mailing lists.

Promotion on social media channels and website

The promotion of the citizens' survey and the information package was strongly supported through 6G4Society's social media channels and dedicated sections on the project website. Regular posts, visual highlights, and targeted announcements were shared on LinkedIn and the digital digest to ensure continuous visibility and encourage participation from diverse audiences.

FIGURE 18: SOCIAL MEDIA SUPPORT FOR THE SURVEY

Social media communication was coordinated with partners to maximise reach, and content was reshared across their respective networks whenever relevant. In addition, the project website featured clearly accessible entry points to the survey and to all components of the information package, including the multilingual infosheets, infographics, and the “What is 6G?” animated video. This integrated online strategy ensured consistent exposure, broadened audience engagement, and supported the wide dissemination of the project’s materials across stakeholder groups.

Events

To foster community engagement and stimulate reflection on the societal implications of 6G, the project organised and participated in 15 workshops and public events across Europe. These activities targeted a broad range of stakeholders, including students, citizens, researchers, industry actors, and civil society organisations, and followed internal guidelines developed to support partners in designing informative, interactive, and value-driven sessions.

The workshops and events included:

- 20×30: Europe’s ADS Summit – Event attendance and interactive booth, May 2024
- “What’s the future of 6G?” – AIESEC Rome interactive workshop, May 2024
- 6G and Social Impacts – Workshop with high school students, October 2024
- Open Living Lab Days – Event participation, September 2024
- Rome Future Week – Session presentation, September 2024
- AIESEC Switzerland Conference – Interactive workshop and booth, November 2024
- Roma Tor Vergata University – Interactive workshop, December 2024
- One Planet Lab, Impact Hub Zurich – Climate community presentation, December 2024

- 6G: Valori, Impatti Sociali e Sostenibilità – A. Einstein High School (2nd edition), February 2025
- 4WARD.earth Climate & Sustainability Meetup – Zurich, May 2025
- 10th STS Italia Conference 2025 – Italy, June 2025
- Looking at the Innovation Triangle in 2030: AI, IoT, and 6G – Belgium, July 2025
- Roma3 University Master in Sociology – Guest lecture, July 2025
- Waag Society Workshop – Amsterdam, September 2025
- Sustainable Places Conference – Milan, October 2025

These events strengthened the project’s outreach, helped test key messages with diverse audiences, and contributed to broader awareness of 6G as a technology with environmental, societal, and ethical implications.

The results of the survey are available in D2.3, “Public positions on 6G Technology”.

SYNERGIES WITH SNS JU AND OTHER RELEVANT PROJECTS AND INITIATIVES

6G4Society, being an integral part of the SNS JU ecosystem, cultivated relations within SNS JU and its projects, as well as other relevant initiatives to amplify the project’s message and grow its reach and relevance.

FIGURE 19: SNS JU NEWSFLASH ON 6G4SOCIETY'S PROFILE ON LINKEDIN

A more detailed overview of these activities is provided in Deliverable D3.1 “Report on Liaison Activities.”

SNS Communication Task Force

The SNS JU maintained a Communication Task Force that brought together all Communication Managers from SNS JU projects. The Task Force met online on a monthly basis to discuss recent communication activities within their respective projects, ongoing collaborations across the ecosystem, and any emerging needs for communication support.

FIGURE 20: COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES INITIATED BY THE SNS TASKFORCE

6G4Society actively participated in this platform to network with other projects, remain informed about the latest communication initiatives within the SNS ecosystem, and promote its own relevant activities, including workshops and the citizens' survey.

6G SNS resources

A dedicated section on the 6G4Society website provided direct access to a wide range of resources from the broader 6G SNS ecosystem. These materials were consistently highlighted and kept up to date to ensure that visitors could easily explore the latest insights and developments in 6G research. The section featured key outputs such as white papers and the SNS JU Journal, offering stakeholders, researchers, and the general public reliable entry points into current discussions and emerging trends within the SNS community. By promoting these resources through both the website and the project's communication channels, 6G4Society contributed to strengthening knowledge exchange and fostering greater awareness of ongoing 6G-related activities across the ecosystem.

FIGURE 21: COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES SUPPORTING THE PROMOTION OF 6G SNS RESOURCES

SNS webinars

The SNS JU regularly organises webinars to promote collaboration across the network's projects and to stimulate discussions on key topics shaping the development of 6G technologies. Throughout the entire duration of the project, 6G4Society consistently promoted these webinars through its communication channels and encouraged stakeholders to participate. The project aimed to join as many sessions as possible, either as an attendee or an active contributor, ensuring continuous engagement with the broader SNS community. 6G4Society participated in an SNS JU webinar in March 2024 and continued its involvement in 2025 by contributing to and attending webinars organised by other SNS JU projects. This sustained participation supported knowledge exchange, visibility, and alignment with ongoing developments within the SNS ecosystem.

6 PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT

The following section presents the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) related to communication and dissemination, the deliverables, and the milestones, as well as a risk assessment and mitigation strategy.

COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION KPIS

The 6G4Society project defined a comprehensive set of Communication and Dissemination KPIs to monitor the results achieved. They are illustrated in the table below.

Name	Indicator	Target number	Number at M24
Scientific publications to journals	Number of scientific publications	4	1
Scientific publications to conference papers	Number of scientific publications	4	5
Scientific workshops attended/organised	Number of scientific workshops	4	17
6G4Society website unique visitors	N. of website unique visitors to 6G4Society website	> 50,000	16,354 visits
Social media followers	N. of followers on LinkedIn, X and Mastodon	> 5,000	1935
Flyers / posters / rollups and other promotional materials	N. of promotional materials done	4	6
Download of policy roadmap, papers, information packages, etc.	N. of downloads of documents on the 6G4Society website	> 1,000	10,875
Digital Digest	N. of digital digests	8	8
Expert interviews / animated graphic videos	N. of videos published on the YouTube channel	>10	10
Citizen's survey	N. of respondents	> 1,000	1'800
Participation in citizens' events and presentations	N. of citizen events / presentations attended	> 15	15
Organisation of Citizens / Policy Makers Forum	N. of participants	> 200	222 members

TABLE 2: COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION KPIS

7 CONCLUSIONS

The 6G4Society project successfully implemented a comprehensive Communication and Dissemination Strategy that ensured **strong visibility, stakeholder engagement, and alignment with the broader objectives of the SNS JU programme**. Through a combination of targeted outreach, strategic partnerships, and multi-channel communication, the project effectively conveyed its mission to explore how 6G innovation can integrate societal, environmental, and economic dimensions from the outset.

The strategy proved instrumental in fostering dialogue across research, industry, policy, and civil society communities. **By maintaining a coherent narrative and consistent messaging, 6G4Society contributed to shaping the broader conversation around responsible and inclusive 6G development in Europe and beyond.**

The project's communication framework, supported by continuous monitoring, evaluation, and adaptation, demonstrated the value of agile and collaborative dissemination practices within the SNS JU ecosystem. The experience gained and tools developed throughout the project can now serve as **a reference for future research and innovation initiatives seeking to embed social responsibility and stakeholder engagement into technological advancement.**